

Recommendation 17:

Gamification

Employee remuneration and incentives

Using 'Gamification' to meet the public sector need 'Employee remuneration and incentives'

Actual solutions and services:

Generally speaking, gamification can be part of every organization's digital business strategy. Within the public sector, gamification can be used to help public agencies run communication campaigns, raise awareness of new or undervalued initiatives, engage citizens, train officials and even change behaviour. To meet the need 'Employee remuneration and incentives', gamification can be used as a way to motivate public employees. Adding game elements to the job is expected to raise motivation, as players take on challenges, receive immediate feedback on their performance, and can compete against others. Building self-esteem and re-enforcing it with peer recognition is a powerful means of unlocking motivation.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- **Availability of a minimal shared language, which enables simplicity and speed in implementation by designers, facilitates widespread adoption by services and systems far away from the entertainment world and shortens the learning curve for users.**
- **Availability of ready-to-use solutions**
- **Enhanced user engagement and motivation**

Opportunities

- **Changing behaviour towards better practices**
- **Increasing IT literacy skills of users**

Weaknesses

- Unclear effects on user attitudes and behaviours.
- One-size-fits-all approach that impedes customization of the game mechanics for specific user groups
- Legal restrictions applying (virtual currencies and virtual assets, data privacy laws and data protection, or labour laws)
- High development costs
- Need for expertise in information systems, organization behaviour and human psychology.

Threats

- Failure by poor design
- Behaviour manipulation and ethical issues – promotion of mechanical behaviours without any improvement of the user experience
- Unrealistic expectations

Employee remuneration and incentives:

When given the choice to improve one aspect of their own job, 36 percent of our public sector informants cited pay, 26 percent said career development, 11 percent said their pension and 81 percent said their organisation had not changed its recruitment practices in light of greater collaboration with the private sector. Sub-needs under this domain include: offering rewards and benefits based on periodic evaluations, pay for performance, getting rid of ineffective incentives systems, formulating a collective wage agreement and offering job security. Certain quotes to highlight the concerns of informants are: "Distorted incentive systems.", "The wages are quite low in comparison with the industry sector.", "Make public sector jobs more attractive, like offering apartments or retirement provisions."

Gamification:

Gamification is the use of game mechanics to drive engagement in non-game business scenarios and to change behaviours in a target audience to achieve business outcomes. Game mechanics such as points, challenges, leaderboards, rules and incentives that make game-play enjoyable are included in these gamified processes.